

Industry 4.0: Digital transformation in production and manufacturing

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ABSTRACT

Digital transformation in the production and manufacturing sector is often implemented using Industry 4.0 technologies. In this research, insights are gained on how COVID-19 affected that transformation. Information is gained via desk research making use of publicly available sources. Three perspectives are applied to a case study within the company Bosch, in particular the Nexeed program which focuses on the Industrial Internet of Things. These perspectives are Business process integration, IT governance and Cybersecurity. COVID-19 has the perspectives of IT governance and Business Process integration, however, it influenced Cyber security. In the case company, COVID-19 worked as a catalyst for the digital transformation.

Keywords

Industry 4.0, Bosch, COVID-19, digital transformation, Nexeed, Predictive maintenance

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Industry 4.0 was already transforming the manufacturing and production sector worldwide before the COVID-19 pandemic. As organizations think about restoring their operations, executives struggle with the longer-term question: How will manufacturing and supply chains look like, and how can we increase resilience in the 'new normal'. To deal with the 'new normal' and potential crises the use of digital technologies is on top of mind for many (Agrawal, Eloot, Mancini & Patel, 2020).

First of all, this report aims to give insights into the potential adjustments of digital transformation policy in large enterprises due to the COVID-19 crisis. This research addresses what IT Governance strategy should be applied regarding the different adoption stages, which are reported by Agrawal et al. (2020) in the McKinsey report 'Industry 4.0: Reimagining manufacturing operations after COVID-19'. Second, this article zooms into the 'deferred adoption' stage combined

with Bosch its industry 4.0 digital transformation. In particular the industry 4.0 pillar 'Connectivity, data, computational power' of Bosch. Hereby the aim is to provide insights into the latest business process integrations from the Nexeed program of Bosch and their potential cybersecurity risks. The main research question that will be addressed is;

How do large manufacturing enterprises execute their industry 4.0, digital transformation and potential cybersecurity risks

SCOPE

For this article, Agrawal et al. (2020) and Bosch (2018) provided useful insights to function as a starting point for this research. Additionally, a number of scientific articles are gathered to zoom in on different IT governance strategies, on the latest digital transformations, business process integration and accompanying potential cybersecurity risks.

Based on the literature, we analyze the three types of adoption stages as stated by 'Agrawal et al. (2020) and the digital transformation of predictive maintenance of Bosch regarding business process integration and cybersecurity risks.

2.0 RESEARCH

This chapter describes the objectives of this research and the approach in which it tends to generate knowledge to achieve the objectives.

2.1 OBJECTIVE

The objective of this research is to gain knowledge of how COVID-19 has affected the digital transformation strategy of the production and manufacturing industry. This research is meant for large companies within the industry. More specifically, it focuses on IT governance, integration of new technologies and potential cybersecurity risks. This paper analyzes if and how large manufacturing industries such as Bosch adjust their execution regarding digital transformation in times of crisis.

2.2 APPROACH

Within this research, knowledge is mainly generated via desk research and news articles. As mentioned earlier the Bosch Nexeed program and the McKinsey report ‘Industry 4.0: Reimagining manufacturing operations after COVID-19’ form the foundation for this research. Chapter 3 provides a relevant overview of the production and manufacturing industry for this particular research. In order to answer the research question: ‘How do large manufacturing enterprises execute their industry 4.0, digital transformation and potential cybersecurity risks?’ This research focuses on the Nexeed program of Bosch. Bosch is a major player in the industry and the Nexeed program in itself is interesting since it started already in 2018.

Chapter 4 divides the analysis into three different subsections. These subsections are IT Governance, Business Process Integration and potential Cybersecurity risks. Useful knowledge from each of these parts is reviewed in the discussion section. When combined it provides comprehensive knowledge to answer the research question.

3 ABOUT PRODUCTION AND MANUFACTURING

Production and manufacturing know many large players worldwide. The industry has close connections towards engineering and industrial design. Examples of production and manufacturing companies in Europe are Volkswagen and Siemens. Large market players in the United States are General Motors and General Electric. The Asian market is dominated by Toyota and Samsung. The production and manufacturing industry are also known about chemical manufacturers such as Shell, PPG and DuPont (Market industry reports, sd). The total market worldwide for production and manufacturing was 846,1 billion dollars in 2019 (Research and markets, 2020). The current expectation for 2020 is a small decrease to \$818,6 and a recovery of + 7% is expected in 2021.

Production and manufacturing can be distinguished in different types (Gupta & Benjaafar, 2004):

- Make to stock: The manufacturer makes products and stores them till the order is placed.
- Make to order: The manufacturer starts production when the order is placed.
- Make to assemble: The manufacturer produces components that can later be assembled.

Specific industry characteristic

A specific characteristic of the production and

manufacturing market is the dependency within the supply chain. This has been emphasized by the outbreak of COVID-19. Furthermore, this was one of the main lessons learned after the consequences of the tsunami in Fukushima, Japan 2011. Companies realized that they had to spread their risks and not rely on one direct supplier. However, more and more of those suppliers are located in China (Linton & Vakil, 2020).

Recent developments

In recent years the development of Industry 4.0 has started. The foundation of Industry 4.0 can be divided into four pillars. Every pillar with each of those making use of different technologies (Agrawal et al., 2020).

Table 1. Industry 4.0 pillars

Industry 4.0 pillar	Technology examples
Connectivity, data, computational power	Sensors, IoT, blockchain
Analytics and Intelligence	Machine learning and AI
Human-machine interaction	VR, AR, chatbots
Advanced engineering	3D printing, renewable energy, nanoparticles

These technologies will be further explored in chapter four of this research and how these technologies are applied in the case company Bosch.

Other, besides Industry 4.0, developments in the production and manufacturing industry are (Bogges, sd):

- From B2B to B2B2C, benefits are for example:
 - Increased profit
 - Faster time to market
 - Brand control
 - Better customer data
- Visibility through big data
- 3D printing

Introduction to the case company

Bosch was founded in 1886 by Robert Bosch

and is currently known as a supplier of technology and services in sectors such as mobility, industrial technology, consumer goods and energy, and building technology. Examples of products that Bosch provides are parts of car engines, cordless power tools, washing machines, fire-detection systems and eBike systems (Bosch, 2020).

Bosch makes active use of Industry 4.0 technologies. For example to predict maintenance by making use of collected data of the production process via sensors that are integrated into the production line, such as ultrasonic or vibration sensors in spindle machines. By analyzing the data it is possible to predict when this spindle will break. Benefits are one side reduced machine downtime and lower maintenance costs (Kohler, sd). Bosch's Nexeed program makes mainly use of the industrial internet of things (IIoT) which is connected to the first pillar 'connectivity, data and computational power (Bosch, 2018).

4 ANALYSIS

In this chapter, an analysis is accomplished with implications for the production and manufacturing industry regarding digital transformation. First, there is an explanation about Industry 4.0 in the case that is used. Subsequently, the analysis is divided into 3 subsections: IT governance, Business Process Integration and Cybersecurity. Each subsection is connected to the Nexeed program and assesses if and how Bosch has made adjustments in response to the COVID-19 crises.

BOSCH INDUSTRY 4.0

Three different forms of digital transformations are possible; quick wins, middle way or long term investments (Agrawal et al., 2020) In April 2018 Bosch released a report about Nexeed, their own software solution for making a connecting factory. Nexeed offers the future of an industry 4.0 solution from source to delivering the final product, see figure 1 (Bosch, 2018). The

following four components are included in Bosch's vision:

1. Software solutions
2. Logistics and manufacturing
3. Service and consulting
4. Field level equipment

In the software solutions for industry 4.0 Bosch has six different products; automation, production performance manager, data analytics, transparency kit, energy platform and IoT gateway. The following are part of Logistics and manufacturing; track and trace, intralogistics execution and data logger. For Service and consulting Bosch does not deliver a solution, it is part of the vision for industry 4.0. The Field level equipment delivers three solutions; Hydraulic compact power unit, Cross-domain development kit and connected industrial sensor solutions. All these solutions will be part of the digital transformation Bosch goes through in the next decade. Regarding the three digital transformation strategies Argrawel et al. (2020) offer, Bosch's digital transformation is going for long term investments.

IT GOVERNANCE AND STRATEGIC SOURCING

With Bosch's release of Nexeed in 2018, the start for their connecting factory is given. To optimize the digital transformation of Bosch from 'traditional' to Nexeed, the IT Governance changed.

PHASES OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

Digital transformation has, according to Deloitte, three steps of adapting; Early, Developing and Maturing (Kane, Palmer, Phillips, Kiron, & Buckley, 2015). In figure 2 we see the top barriers by every maturity stage. When looking at Bosch we see a clear strategy, a lot of priorities but sufficient tech skills (Bosch, 2020). Therefore, Bosch's position fits the developing phase of digital transformation.

GOVERNANCE DESIGN MATRIX

Weill (2004) considers five different IT decision domains (see figure 3), for every domain the governance can be designed at separate levels.

IT PRINCIPLES

The CIO in Bosch reports to the CDO and CTO (Lamml, J. 2019). Regarding the Design Matrix from Weill (2004), the current style is IT duopoly.

Bosch has already started with Nexeed in 2018. Considering the article of Lamml (2019) before starting the Nexeed programma the IT governance for IT principles was an IT duopoly. However, for Bosch to prepare their digital transformation for the 'new normal' the best governance for IT principles is IT Duopoly, where IT executives and CxO or BU leaders have the decision rights or input rights for particular IT decisions. Therefore, Bosch needs governance from IT executives and CxO or BU leaders to make the right decisions. The IT duopoly archetype has multiple advantages in comparison to the other archetypes, namely:

1. It only evolves two decision parties
2. The IT group is one of the groups that sees Bosch as a whole and therefore can look at opportunities with other business units.

Bosch their IT Governance should be a corporate IT group that has a duopoly with each business unit (Weill, Ross, 2004). Bosch has nothing to change for IT principles.

IT INVESTMENT AND PRIORITIZATION

For IT investment and prioritization, the duopoly governance style also satisfies the most. Again, the combination of an IT group that sees the whole company and look for opportunities with each business unit will satisfy Bosch the most.

In the research of Weill (2004) firms that rate IT governance high (as does Bosch as well) typically use IT duopolies for IT principles and investments. For this reason, we only looked at the result of those two domains.

Weill (2004) shows the three most popular combinations of decision domains and IT governance styles among 256 firms (Weill, et al. 2004). Figure 3 shows the most common variant that is applicable for Bosch because of the combination domain/style from IT principles and

Domain Style	IT principles	IT architecture	IT infrastructure	Business application needs	IT investment and prioritization
Business Monarchy					
IT Monarchy		1	1		
Feudal					
Federal				1	
Duopoly	1				1
Anarchy					

IT investment and prioritization.

The digital transformation Bosch is going

through will need IT kind of view, if the digital transformation is not IT minded. The long term investment will probably not be as imagined. The level of industry 4.0 in their digital transformation will need IT experts. Therefore, this type of IT Governance can help the adoption of the 'new normal'.

By preparing for the 'new normal' Bosch should, in combination with the IT Governance, think of being more resilient. A recent Mckinsey survey found out that 93 percent of manufacturing companies focus on being more resilient (Mayank Agrawal, Mancini, Patel. 2020). Therefore, the use of IT Duopoly on IT principles is an argumentative choice. With this IT Governance, Bosch is more resilient and prepared for the digital transformation to the 'new normal'.

Bosch has not changed its IT Governance when the pandemic hit. They already had chosen their Industry 4.0 / digital transformation path with Nexeed.

BUSINESS PROCESS INTEGRATION

When implementing Industry 4.0 various business processes will have to adapt their products and services in conjunction with the changing environment, market or taking advantage of new opportunities.

Figure 3: Traditional maintenance scheduling versus predictive maintenance for assets. Source: Analytics Mason, 2013

In 2013 Hilton explained the advantages of using internet of Things (IoT) and Machine to Machine (M2M) for predictive maintenance (Hilton, 2013). The advantage over traditional maintenance is that IoT/M2M helps lower operating and capital costs by facilitating proactive servicing and repair assets using more efficient repair resources as opposed to a more reactive traditional approach.

As can be observed in figure 4, repair resources can be used more efficiently using predictive maintenance planning for assets compared to the traditional methods (Mason, 2013). To enable these advantages three major solutions enhancements can be made (Hilton, 2013):

The first solution is by capturing sensor data. By adding sensors on the assets being monitored, a

constant flow of data is recorded and compared to the standard ranges of tolerance on whether assets are behaving as expected.

The second solution is facilitating data communications. The flowing data off these sensors are to be connected to a processing facility using some WAN- or LAN-based connectivity platform depending on factors such as technology used, security requirements, level of asset mobility, etc.

The final solution includes creating the prediction. Using a business intelligence system (that is based on expert knowledge) data is continuously evaluated. With a strict series of rules expected and observed data is associated with the monitored assets in order to create predictions on the progressive deterioration of the asset. Which would allow the company to match its cash expenditure on maintenance with the actual prevention of asset wear-and-tear.

In order to more clearly observe the differences between the traditional and predictive maintenance methods figure 5 had been created. (See appendix A for a zoomed-in view.)

In the case of Bosch, predictive maintenance was implemented using the Nexeed Maintenance support system (Nexeed MSS), which is a system that is used for maintenance processes, troubleshooting, as well as preventive and predictive maintenance (Bastian et al., 2018). For example, when an asset is about to overheat or if a part(s) are showing signs of wear. Rather than having to schedule in many maintenance periods Nexeed allows for more efficient maintenance scheduling by matching maintenance activity of actual and predicted symptoms of future asset failures (Bosch Connected Industry, 2020). By monitoring defined parameters in the production process and sending notifications when a warning limit is exceeded, the out-of-service times can be reduced. Using a ticket management application Bosch can automatically optimize servicing schedules with tickets that are sorted by urgency (Bosch Connected Industry, 2020). By combining the ticket management application and maintenance scheduling vital resources are saved by reducing

the need to purchase replacement parts of assets before they fail and out-of-service times are reduced by optimizing when maintenance must be completed. As a result since the rollout, within the Bamberg plant a reduction of 20% in average interruption time and an increase of up to 5 percent in overall equipment effectiveness(OEE) can be observed (Bastian et al., 2018).

Implementing a predictive maintenance system had a number of implications for Bosch. The most important implication was the creation of the Nexeed MSS system. As traditional maintenance is very simplistic compared to predictive maintenance, many resources are required to create and implement the Nexeed IAS system. This is because the entire system requires many different components, such as sensors, a communication platform, expert system, ticket management applications etc. As a result of implementing the new system, the maintenance workforce would also have to be trained to use the new Nexeed system. Another implication is that it allows enterprises to innovate through new revenue streams, such as enhanced warranty and strengthen competitive advantage through a differentiated offering (Hilton, 2013).

CYBERSECURITY

As mentioned before, Bosch is implementing sensors to predict maintenance. These sensors are run by software, called Nexeed, which enables Bosch to monitor the machines (Bosch, 2018). This Industry 4.0 innovation enables the company to converge software and manufacturing, but it also brings some cybersecurity risks.

Here is a list of a number of risks:

1. The system Nexeed, the operating system of the sensors, could be infiltrated by malicious software which could result in a less efficient working device. Someone with malicious motives could make the true status of the machines invisible for the employees. A result of this could be that the machines would be damaged and that the production stands still
2. In the same way the sensors could be altered in a way where the machines become unsafe for the employees. An example of this could be the cooling systems.
3. In the 'Connectivity, data, computational power' part of Bosch it is stated that the sensors are connected in the internal environment. This means that a virus, for example the Stuxnet, could infiltrate in the system and spread around the network. This could result in a shut down of the

supply chain.

4. It could be possible for hackers to change the speed of the machines by injecting a virus in the software of the sensors.

The supply chain is a crucial part of all manufacturing organizations. With the implementation of intelligent, connected platforms and devices, the supply chains have evolved to digital supply networks (Waslo, Lewis, Hajj, 2017). For the management, this means that they have better efficiency, a better overview of the products and the possibility to meet the customers requirements more. With this also comes a higher cybersecurity threat. Here are some potential cybersecurity threats for manufactures implementing industry 4.0:

5. Industry 4.0 has transformed supply chains to whole networks with a constant traffic of data in the network. A possible risk that comes with this, is the potential of a data breach or leak. Financial or sensitive information can be stolen and for example end up at the competitors.
6. The algorithms of AI and IoT devices can be manipulated. This can be disastrous for a company, because it can result in an unsafe environment, a shutdown or a damage on the brands of the goods.

Table 2. Risk analysis

Security risk	Severity→		
	Low	Med	High
1			High
2			High
3			High
4			High
5		Med	
6			High

As it is shown in the matrix, the severity of the cyber risks is high. Although the likelihood isn't as high as the damage of the outcomes, it is still important to mitigate these risks. An outcome of, for example, risk 1,2,3 or 4 could result in severe health issues of employees or significant damage to the company itself.

A first step to reduce these risks would be to

reduce the attack surface. This begins with the manufactures of the sensors and other IoT devices. This starts at the manufactures of these devices. Buying companies should make sure that they buy the products for their industry 4.0 network at a vendor with great network and security designs. The security of these products should come from two ways, from the vendor and the buyers (Waslo et al., 2017).

Also, because companies are now in the phase of shifting to industry 4.0, it would be smart to implement cybersecurity in the products from the start. It is a lot harder to enforce cybersecurity in a supply chain when the processes are already implemented.

Like mentioned before, DSN supply chain models use a lot of data. In order to ensure the safety and confidentiality of the data, companies should use top cloud solutions, strong encryption, responsive threat detection and strong intrusion prevention solutions. Because of the severity of the outcomes, it is recommended to outsource a great part of the security to a company who is specialized in cybersecurity.

5 DISCUSSION

When manufacturing companies decide to digitize their production system and ultimately implement industry 4.0 a number of factors have to be considered.

One such factor is financial, as most companies in this industry often use very traditional production methods and systems, a variety of costly changes have to be made. This can be seen through the three perspectives analyzed in this paper. As stated, when adopting industry 4.0 the optimal governance matrix strategy focuses on having an IT duopoly. With manufacturing companies typically being slow to adopt new IT solutions and processes, an argument can be made that most companies in the sector are not IT focused. Thus, many would have to change their IT governance structure for the digital transformation to take place. Thus, financial resources have to be used to swift the organizational structure to optimize it for the new normal.

In terms of business processes, supply chain networks and cybersecurity many considerations have to be made. The adoption of Industry 4.0 can often be considered a big project that is costly in terms of resources, such as financial, human and time. Some of the considerations that have to be made include whether to invest their financial and human resources into research and development of industry 4.0 solutions or creating budgets for outsourcing the software development to a specialized organization such as Bosch Connected

Industries. Subsequently, a detailed financial plan has to be created outlining which processes are built inhouse versus which are outsourced and how the cybersecurity of those processes are ensured through inhouse development or outsourced security.

With the current Covid-19 situation companies are put in a position where they have to speed up their digital transformation. One of the first major decisions on this part is the choice to implement Industry 4.0 yourself or to outsource it to IT firms who are specialized in this. One of the benefits of outsourcing could be that the implementation of the new hardware and software could be done much quicker. Bosch would also carry less responsibility on the cybersecurity part. However, by maintaining the IT parts themselves, Bosch could have more control on the processes. When combined with the IT duopoly archetype, the process leaders can gain a significant amount of control on the processes in the supply chain.

Before the choice can be made whether to outsource the digital transformation or not, it also has to be clear where in the processes certain controls have to be implemented to mitigate risks, who the owners are and how an outsourced IT company would maintain this. It is also recommended that in the same assessment a new risk analysis is done by an external party. This is to make an outline of the potential cost and chance of a risk when it is outsourced. The best option for Bosch would be to maintain it themselves. This gives Bosch the opportunity for new business opportunities to implement Nexeed in other companies. The IT governance allows this and with this Bosch also enhances their knowledge on the cybersecurity part of the software.

6 CONCLUSION

In this paper the main question was; How do large manufacturing enterprises execute their industry 4.0, digital transformation and potential cybersecurity risks?

For the digital transformation of Bosch there is no change regarding their execution. Bosch already adopted Nexeed. The vision of Bosch on their ITG is not changed during the pandemic. The vision on their ITG may not have changed, but their approach on cybersecurity must have developed in the digital transformation of Bosch. The implementation of Industry 4.0 and the multiple IoT devices came with a lot of risks. Risks that could cost Bosch a lot of financial assets in a worst-case scenario.

However, the implementation of Nexeed has brought a lot of good things for the supply chain of Bosch. With the right ITG and cybersecurity

measures it could enhance the digital transformation of Bosch to whole new depths. Implementing industry 4.0 also included many changes in terms of business processes. As a result, a value creation network can be created for companies adopting the concept through connecting networks across company boundaries. By integrating many different software systems and business processes between, various companies in the supply chain, communication and efficiency could be improved. This integration would thus not only benefit Bosch, but the production and manufacturing industry as a whole.

REFERENCES

- Bastian, S., Hüttenhein, C., Hellwig, M., Klose, J., Massold, W., & Paulus-Rohmer, D. et al. (2018). From Lean to Industry 4.0 – More than just the Vision of a Smart Factory [White paper]. Retrieved October 1, 2020, from Robert Bosch Manufacturing Solutions GmbH: <https://afia.pt/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/Whitepaper.pdf>
- Bogges, M. 10 Trends That Will Dominate Manufacturing in 2019. Retrieved from <https://global.hitachi-solutions.com/blog/top-manufacturing-trends>
- Bosch Connected Industry. (2020). Predictive maintenance. Bosch Connected Industry. Retrieved 30 September 2020, from <https://www.bosch-connected-industry.com/de/en/plant-operator/reduce-machine-downtimes/predictive-maintenance/>.
- Bosch. (2018). NEXEED - software and services for production and logistics. Retrieved from https://assets.bosch.com/media/en/global/products_and_solutions/connected_products_and_services/industry_40/bosch-connected-industry-brochure.pdf
- Bosch. (2018). Predictive maintenance with the Nexeed Industrial Application System. Retrieved from https://assets.bosch.com/media/global/bosch_group/our_figures/pdf/bosch-today-2020.pdf
- Bosch. (2020). Bosch Today 2020. Retrieved from https://assets.bosch.com/media/global/bosch_group/our_figures/pdf/bosch-today-2020.pdf
- Edwards B; Hofmeyr S; Forrest S; Hype and heavy tails: A closer look at data breaches. Retrieved from <https://academic.oup.com/cybersecurity/article/2/1/3/2736315>
- Gupta, D., & Benjaafar, S. (2004). Make-to-order, make-to-stock, or delay product differentiation? A common framework for modeling and analysis. IIE Transactions, 36(6), 529-546. doi:10.1080/07408170490438519
- Hilton, S. (2013). IoT and predictive maintenance [Blog]. Retrieved 30 September 2020, from <https://blog.bosch-si.com/industry40/iot-predictive-maintenance/>.
- Kane, G. C., Palmer, D., Phillips, A. N., Kiron, D., & Buckley, N. (2015). Strategy, not technology, drives digital transformation. MIT Sloan Management Review and Deloitte University Press, 14(1-25).
- Kohler, M. Industry 4.0: Predictive maintenance use cases in detail. Retrieved from <https://blog.bosch-si.com/industry40/industry-4-0-predictive-maintenance-use-cases-in-detail/>
- Lamml, J. (2019) Bosch ernennt Vijay Ratnaparkhe zum CIO. Retrieved from <https://www.cio.de/a/bosch-ernennt-vijay-ratnaparkhe-zum-cio.3605914>
- Linton, T., & Vakil, B. (2020). Coronavirus Is Proving We Need More Resilient Supply Chains. Harvard business review. Retrieved from <https://hbr.org/2020/03/coronavirus-is-proving-that-we-need-more-resilient-supply-chains>
- Market industry reports Retrieved from <https://www.marketresearchreports.com/industry-manufacturing>
- Mayank Agrawal, K. E., Matteo Mancini, Alpesh Patel. (2020). Industry 4.0: Reimagining manufacturing operations after COVID-19. Retrieved from <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/operations/our-insights/industry-4-0-reimagining-manufacturing-operations-after-covid-19>
- Refsdal, A.; Solhaug, B.; Stolen K. Cyber-Risk Management page 15-25 Retrieved from <https://link.springer.com/content/pdf/10.1007%2F978-3-319-23570-7.pdf>
- Research and markets. (2020). Insights into the Worldwide General Manufacturing Industry to 2030 - How the Market is Likely to Emerge and Grow After COVID-19. Retrieved from <https://www.globenewswire.com/news-release/2020/05/05/2027353/0/en/Insights-into-the-Worldwide-General-Manufacturing-Industry-to-2030-How-the-Market-is-Likely-to-Emerge-and-Grow-After-COVID-19.html>
- Robert Bosch Manufacturing Solutions GmbH. (2020). *Digitalization in times of COVID-19* [White paper]. Retrieved October 1, 2020, from Robert Bosch Manufacturing Solutions GmbH: https://www.bosch-connected-industry.com/de/media/en/loesungen/downloads/digitalisierung_in_corona-zeiten.pdf
- Waslo, R., Lewis T., Hajj R. (2017) Industry 4.0 and cybersecurity managing risks in an age of connected production. Retrieved from https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/insights/us/articles/3749_Industry4-0_cybersecurity/DUP_Industry4-0_cybersecurity.pdf
- Weill, P., & Ross, J. W. (2004). IT Governance: How Top Performers Manage IT Decision Rights for Superior Results.